

Multimodal Green Branding: A Critical Discourse Analysis of Sustainability Narratives in The Body Shop and L'Oréal Paris

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Abstract

This study investigates the construction of green branding and the potential presence of greenwashing in the marketing strategies of The Body Shop and L'Oréal. Using a multimodal critical discourse analysis approach, the research examines both verbal and visual elements from official websites and social media platforms to explore how these brands convey their environmental commitments. The findings reveal that The Body Shop consistently demonstrates authentic green branding through transparent messaging and visuals that emphasize ethical practices and sustainability initiatives. In contrast, L'Oréal's communication, while highlighting scientific innovation and future goals, often lacks specific and verifiable actions, raising concerns about the risk of greenwashing. By integrating perspectives from recent literature on green branding and greenwashing, this study highlights the importance of coherence and transparency in building credible environmental brand identities. The insights provided contribute to a deeper understanding of how brands shape consumer perceptions in the era of sustainability marketing, offering practical implications for marketers and future research directions.

1. Introduction

In recent years, there has been a growing awareness of environmental issues, prompting companies to adopt branding strategies that emphasize an eco-friendly (go green) image. According to a report by (Deloitte Indonesia Perspectives, 2024) over 60% of Indonesian consumers tend to purchase environmentally friendly products. Furthermore, data from the Indonesian Retail Entrepreneurs Association (APRINDO), as cited by (Akbari, Biran, 2023) on Kompasiana, confirmed that this trend has been evident since 2020, with an increase of 30% at that time. With the rise in public awareness and shifting consumer preferences, many brands have begun to adapt to market demands that favor healthier and more environmentally friendly products. Today, more people have become aware of the environmental damage caused by single-use products that generate waste, carbon emissions leading to air pollution, and there is a growing desire to conserve energy by utilizing natural resources or advanced technologies.

(Hartono, Kornelius, n.d., 2023) found that consumers are drawn to purchasing eco-friendly lighting products, such as Philips LED bulbs, due to the brand's positive environmental contributions. Similarly, an earlier study by (Pinem et al., 2018) revealed that 98% of 50 respondents were influenced to buy products carrying an eco-friendly label. The implementation of green branding strategies has extended across a wide variety of everyday consumer goods. Beyond food products, this approach has been adopted in sectors such as automotive, fashion, cosmetics, and skincare. Thiallocate a substantial portion of their spending towards shopping (McKinsey dalam ("Mengungkap Kebiasaan Belanja Generasi Z: Perubahan Dalam Dunia Konsumen," 2023) . These shifting preferences present significant opportunities for companies to promote green and sustainable products in response to growing market demand.

Green branding is a marketing strategy aimed at establishing a company's image as environmentally responsible by emphasizing eco-friendly attributes in both products and corporate communications (Velita & Suson, 2023). This strategy plays a crucial role in shaping positive consumer perceptions, fostering brand loyalty, and encouraging repeat purchases. For example, The Body Shop consistently promotes sustainability and social justice values in its marketing campaigns, which has become a cornerstone of its green branding efforts (Dellyana & Aldianto, 2024). However, alongside the rise of green marketing trends, the phenomenon of greenwashing has also proliferated. Greenwashing refers to companies exaggerating or fabricating their environmental claims to attract eco-conscious consumers, without substantial actions to support those claims (Seele & Gatti, 2017). Such practices not only mislead consumers but also undermine public trust in genuine sustainability initiatives even minor discrepancies between environmental claims and actual corporate behavior can significantly damage consumer perceptions and erode brand credibility.

Recent studies reveal that greenwashing negatively affects green brand equity and consumers' purchase intentions (Akturan, Ulun, 2018) From a critical perspective, the potential danger of greenwashing lies in its ability to manipulate consumer perception, leading to what (Lyon & Montgomery, 2015) describe as "consumer deception," where buyers may believe they are making ethical choices while unintentionally supporting unsustainable practices. For researchers and consumers alike, recognizing these strategies is essential to distinguish genuine environmental commitment from superficial marketing ploys. Furthermore, (Isac et al., 2024), through a bibliometric review, emphasizes that greenwashing fosters public skepticism and reduces customer buying intention toward brands perceived as inauthentic.

Green products, or eco-friendly products, are designed, manufactured, and distributed with an explicit goal of minimizing environmental harm. This involves the utilization of natural ingredients, sustainable production methods, and significant efforts to reduce waste and emissions (Fachrurazi et al., 2022). These products are not only intended to lessen the carbon footprint but are also perceived to embody superior quality due to environmentally conscious production processes (Grant, John, 2007). Growing consumer preference for green products is closely linked to their perceived environmental safety, health benefits, and alignment with ethical and sustainable business values. Furthermore, the rising popularity of eco-conscious lifestyles and the promise of long-term economic and environmental efficiency have positioned green products as an attractive choice in the marketplace.

The Body Shop and L'Oréal Paris represent two prominent cosmetics brands that have strategically integrated sustainability narratives into their branding, albeit with different approaches and depth of commitment. The Body Shop, a pioneer of ethical beauty from the United Kingdom, is renowned for its use of natural ingredients and its long-standing opposition to animal testing. Since its expansion into Indonesia in 1992, The Body Shop has reinforced its commitment to sustainability, operating 15 stores nationwide while consistently promoting its environmental

advocacy (Salsabila & Rubiyanti, 2022). As stated on its official website (www.thebodyshop.com), the company has championed green retail spaces for over four decades, underlining its belief in transformative business practices and the inherent beauty of every woman. The Body Shop positions itself not merely as a cosmetics retailer but as an activist brand, aiming to cultivate a more beautiful and ethical world.

Conversely, L'Oréal, a global cosmetics conglomerate headquartered in Paris, originally built its reputation on hair color products in 1979 before expanding into a wide portfolio of beauty brands for both men and women. L'Oréal frames its sustainability efforts within a broader narrative of corporate responsibility and social contribution, claiming to foster positive societal impact through various initiatives. According to its official communications (www.loreal.com), the company emphasizes responsible and sustainable operations as central to its business ethos. Notably, as reported by (Agmasari, Silvita, 2015), L'Oréal has made measurable strides toward environmental sustainability and focusing on reducing plastic waste, water usage, and CO2 emissions. However, given its vast global footprint and complex supply chains, critical scrutiny is warranted to determine whether these sustainability claims reflect genuine transformative practices or function primarily as strategic green branding to appeal to increasingly eco-aware consumers.

Along with the campaigns and visions promoted by The Body Shop and L'Oréal as part of their sales strategies, questions arise regarding the extent to which these strategies genuinely reflect sustainable practices or merely serve as marketing tactics (greenwashing). Both companies strive to construct a brand image that emphasizes environmental consciousness and contributes to human well-being. This branding approach is clearly intended to attract potential consumers who share similar values and interests. Therefore, this study aims to examine how these two companies build their sustainability image through a multimodal approach in branding.

In the context of this study, the theories of green branding and greenwashing are highly relevant for analyzing how The Body Shop and L'Oréal construct their green brand images. By understanding the dynamics of these two concepts, this research can assess the extent to which these brands genuinely practice sustainability or fall into greenwashing practices. Furthermore, this approach enables an evaluation of whether the green images projected by these brands have a positive impact or pose risks to consumers through misleading claims (NGUYEN et al., 2021).

Language possesses a unique characteristic in that whenever we communicate, we consciously adapt our expressions to suit the existing context. Yet, at the same time, our choice of words and manner of expression actively construct and define that context. The language and imagery they use are not only tailored to their audience, but also work to actively build a particular brand identity. As (Fairclough, 1995) argues, discourse is both socially shaped and socially shaping; it reflects the context while simultaneously constructing it. Companies carefully select specific words, colors, and visual styles to reflect values such as eco-friendliness, luxury, or inclusivity. (Kress, Gunther & Leewen, Theo van, 2006) further explain that multimodal texts communicate meaning through the interplay of various semiotic resources, such as visual design, layout, and typography, which work alongside verbal language to produce persuasive messages. In doing so, brands do not merely respond to consumer expectations but actively shape them, reinforcing certain ideas and emotions associated with their identity. Through Critical Discourse Analysis (CDA) and multimodal analysis, we can uncover how these choices subtly influence public perception, constructing a narrative that aligns with the company's goals and market positioning.

In the case of The Body Shop and L'Oréal, this process is particularly evident. The Body Shop, for example, consistently uses natural imagery, earthy color schemes, and language emphasizing sustainability and ethical sourcing. Phrases such as 'enriched with community trade ingredients' or 'forever against animal testing' not only appeal to environmentally conscious consumers but also construct a strong, authentic eco-friendly brand identity (Lamila, Princess, 2007). Meanwhile, L'Oréal, while traditionally associated with luxury and glamour, has increasingly incorporated green initiatives and visual elements that suggest environmental responsibility,

such as promoting biodegradable formulas and sustainable packaging. However, as (Van Dijk, Teun, 1988) points out, discourse strategies are often employed to subtly manage public opinion, which invites critical examination of whether these green claims represent deep ethical commitments or strategic branding maneuvers. The multimodal strategies of these two brands differ significantly in intensity and focus, offering a rich ground for comparative analysis.

By applying CDA and multimodal frameworks, we can critically examine how both brands construct their green identities, not merely as a reflection of market trends but as active participants in shaping consumer attitudes towards ethical consumption. This analysis can reveal the underlying power relations and ideologies embedded in their branding strategies, highlighting whether these representations are genuinely transformative or simply performative gestures to capture the growing eco-conscious market.

While prior studies have largely explored consumer perceptions or the effectiveness of green marketing strategies in isolation, limited attention has been paid to the multimodal construction of green branding narratives, particularly in comparative contexts. The Body Shop and L'Oréal Paris, both global beauty giants, actively promote sustainability in their brand messaging, yet the depth and authenticity of their claims remain open to scrutiny. Amid growing global concerns over greenwashing and increasing regulatory pressure on environmental marketing claims, this study fills an important gap by conducting a critical multimodal discourse analysis of these two brands. By dissecting visual, verbal, and symbolic modes, this research not only advances academic discussions in multimodal analysis and green marketing discourse but also offers practical insights for consumers, policymakers, and industry practitioners striving for transparency and genuine sustainability in corporate branding.

This research employs a Multimodal Critical Discourse Analysis (MCDA) approach to examine the textual and visual strategies used by these brands. MCDA provides a comprehensive framework for analyzing how language and visuals work together to construct meanings. By focusing on the green branding discourse of The Body Shop and L'Oréal, this study aims to uncover how these companies position themselves as environmentally responsible brands and the extent to which their narratives align with authentic sustainable practices.

2. Materials and Methods

This research employs a qualitative approach, combining Critical Discourse Analysis (CDA) and multimodal analysis to examine how The Body Shop and L'Oréal construct their green branding narratives. CDA is applied to explore how language choices reflect power relations, ideologies, and environmental commitments promoted by these brands. Complementing this, multimodal analysis enables a deeper examination of visual elements such as color schemes, symbols of nature, and overall imagery that work alongside textual strategies to project eco-friendly identities.

The data consist of digital advertisements and promotional materials published by The Body Shop and L'Oréal between 2022 and 2025. These materials were collected from the brands' official websites and social media platforms, including Instagram and Facebook, focusing on campaigns that explicitly claim environmental responsibility or use green visual aesthetics. Data collection was conducted through documentation techniques by archiving these digital materials for further analysis.

The analysis follows the framework proposed by (Fairclough & Fairclough, 2012) for CDA and (Kress, Gunther & Leewen, Theo van, 2006) model for multimodal analysis. Particular attention is given to verbal expressions such as environmental jargon and narratives of sustainability, as well as visual strategies including the use of green colors, natural imagery, and

representations of eco-friendly products. Furthermore, this study evaluates the alignment of these messages with green branding principles (White, K. et al., 2019) and assesses potential indicators of greenwashing based on the perspectives of (De Freitas Netto et al., 2020). This integrated approach allows for a comprehensive understanding of how these brands construct their green image and whether such portrayals might pose risks of misleading consumers.

3. Results and Discussion

This study focuses on comparing the communication strategies employed by The Body Shop and L'Oréal in constructing their green image through both linguistic and visual elements in their advertisements. The analysis adopts Critical Discourse Analysis and Multimodal Analysis approaches to explore the interplay between language choices, visual imagery, and the sustainability ideologies that these brands seek to project. Theories of green branding and greenwashing also serve as a framework to assess the authenticity of the environmental messages conveyed by both brands, while identifying potential risks for consumers when such messages turn out to be more manipulative than genuine.

No	Brands	Data Type	Data	Sources
1	The Body Shop	Verbal	"Enrich Not Exploit", "Forever Against Animal Testing", "100% Vegan"	www.thebodyshop.com, Instagram @thebodyshop
2	The Body Shop	Visual	 Green leaves	Website resmi, Instagram, Facebook
			 Vegan on shea butter	
			 recycled plastic"	
	The Body Shop	Visual		Instagram @thebodyshop,

				Facebook The Body Shop Official
			<p>Campaign: refill station</p>	
			<p>Activism: no animals testing</p>	
4	L'Oréal	Verbal	"L'Oréal for the Future", "Green Science for Beauty", "Because you're worth it"	www.loreal.com, Instagram @lorealparis
5	L'Oréal	Visual		Website resmi, Instagram, Facebook
			<p>Green packaging</p>	
			<p>Laboratorium</p>	
			<p>Innovation in Beauty</p>	

6	L'Oréal	Visual	<p>sustainability report</p>	Sustainability Report 2023, Instagram @lorealparis
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Figure 1: Research Data

In terms of language use, The Body Shop consistently presents a strong sustainability narrative by employing expressions such as "ethical", "cruelty-free", and "enrich not exploit". These word choices not only build a positive image but also reinforce their commitment to sustainability values. In contrast, L'Oréal frequently uses broader terms like "green science" and "powered by nature", which sound progressive but remain relatively abstract. This tendency may reflect an attempt to capitalize on the green trend without providing verifiable claims, as highlighted in the concept of greenwashing (De Freitas Netto et al., 2020). A critical examination of these narratives reveals that The Body Shop appears to be more transparent and specific, while L'Oréal tends to deliver a more generic environmental message.

From the visual perspective, The Body Shop employs natural color palettes such as green and brown, along with imagery of leaves, plants, and raw ingredients in their advertisements. These visuals strengthen their verbal messages and enhance the authenticity of their sustainability practices. Meanwhile, L'Oréal often adopts more futuristic visuals with bright green hues and technological elements, creating a modern impression that may blur the natural essence typically emphasized in genuine green campaigns (White, K. et al., 2019). The multimodal analysis shows that The Body Shop consistently aligns text and visuals to support their green image, whereas L'Oréal appears to rely on visual appeal to create an illusion of sustainability without substantial narrative depth.

Synthesizing these findings, it can be concluded that The Body Shop tends to apply a more authentic green branding strategy compared to L'Oréal, which in some aspects exhibits signs of greenwashing. Consumers are more likely to perceive The Body Shop's sustainability message as clear and consistent, reducing the risk of feeling misled. On the other hand, L'Oréal's more generalized messaging and aesthetically driven visuals have the potential to confuse consumers who are increasingly critical of corporate green claims (Delmas & Burbano, 2011). Thus, this analysis does not only reveal how both brands construct their image but also offers a critical reflection on the importance of clarity and honesty in green marketing communications.

This section presents an integrated analysis of verbal and visual data collected from The Body Shop and L'Oréal, applying a multimodal critical discourse analysis framework. The analysis aims to uncover how each brand constructs its green identity through linguistic choices and visual representations, and to assess whether these strategies align with authentic green branding or suggest elements of greenwashing

For The Body Shop, verbal elements such as the slogan "Enrich Not Exploit" and the phrase "Forever Against Animal Testing" reflect a strong commitment to ethical and sustainable practices. These verbal messages are reinforced visually through imagery of natural elements like green leaves, shea butter, and refill stations, which emphasize the brand's environmental initiatives. Through this combination, The Body Shop positions itself as a pioneer of ethical beauty, aiming to build trust and emotional connection with environmentally conscious consumers.

In contrast, L'Oréal's communication emphasizes innovation and scientific advancement in sustainability, as reflected in the campaign "L'Oréal for the Future" and the claim "Green Science for Beauty". Visually, the brand uses bright green tones and laboratory imagery to convey progress and technological solutions for environmental challenges. However, according to recent insights on greenwashing (Akturan, Ulun, 2018; Seele & Gatti, 2017), such reliance on

technological narratives and ambiguous claims requires careful scrutiny. While L'Oréal presents measurable efforts such as carbon reduction infographics and recycled packaging initiatives, it remains necessary to critically examine whether these claims represent substantial change or predominantly serve as image-enhancing strategies.

By applying a multimodal lens, this analysis highlights how both brands not only reflect their target audiences but also actively construct consumer perceptions of environmental responsibility. The findings will help determine whether these practices genuinely contribute to sustainable development or risk misleading consumers through greenwashing tactics.

3.1. Interpretation

The preliminary findings of this study reveal distinctive approaches adopted by The Body Shop and L'Oréal in constructing their green branding identities. The Body Shop demonstrates a more consistent and transparent narrative of environmental responsibility. The use of explicit language such as "Forever Against Animal Testing" and visual representations of natural ingredients not only reinforces their ethical stance but also reflects an integrated green branding strategy. Furthermore, The Body Shop's emphasis on community trade and refill stations suggests genuine efforts towards sustainable consumer engagement, minimizing the potential for greenwashing.

Conversely, L'Oréal presents a more complex positioning. While the brand effectively incorporates sustainability themes through phrases like "Green Science for Beauty" and visuals of eco-friendly technologies, there is a noticeable reliance on scientific rhetoric and generalized commitments. According to (Akturan, Ulun, 2018; Seele & Gatti, 2017) such strategies can blur the line between genuine sustainability and greenwashing, particularly when specific outcomes are not transparently communicated. The emphasis on future goals rather than current achievements may raise questions about the depth of L'Oréal's environmental commitment.

Overall, these preliminary insights suggest that The Body Shop positions itself closer to the ideal of green branding, integrating clear, relatable narratives and visual cues that resonate with environmentally conscious consumers. Meanwhile, L'Oréal, despite its substantial investments in sustainable innovation, risks being perceived as engaging in greenwashing due to its more abstract and technologically focused messaging.

4. Conclusion

This study has explored the construction of green branding and the potential presence of greenwashing in the marketing communications of The Body Shop and L'Oréal, utilizing a multimodal critical discourse analysis approach. By examining the interplay between verbal language and visual elements across official websites and social media platforms, the research has identified clear distinctions in how both brands position themselves within the green marketing space.

The Body Shop emerges as a brand that successfully integrates authentic green branding strategies. Its consistent use of transparent messaging, combined with visual representations of natural elements and ethical initiatives, reinforces its image as an environmentally responsible company. Moreover, The Body Shop's initiatives, such as refill stations and fair-trade sourcing, not only respond to environmental concerns but also build consumer trust and loyalty.

In contrast, L'Oréal, despite its significant investment in sustainability, presents a more ambiguous image. While its communication highlights innovation and future-oriented goals, the reliance on broad claims and scientific narratives can dilute consumer perception of genuine

environmental commitment. As (Seele & Gatti, 2017) and (Akturan, Ulun, 2018) suggest, such strategies risk falling into the category of greenwashing, especially when specific, verifiable actions are not prominently featured. This raises critical questions about the balance between marketing appeal and substantive environmental impact in corporate communications.

Overall, the study concludes that The Body Shop offers a stronger example of authentic green branding, while L'Oréal demonstrates the complexities and potential pitfalls of sustainability marketing. These findings underline the importance of transparency and coherence in building credible green brand identities, providing valuable insights for marketers and consumers alike. Future research could expand this analysis by incorporating consumer reception data to further assess the impact of multimodal strategies on brand perception and trust.

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